

EXTRACTION OF IRON FROM THE TAILINGS OF “ALMALK MMC” JSC

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Abstract: The technology of extracting iron from the tailings of a copper concentrator has been studied. Ammonium sulfate is used as a reducing agent and the effect of the firing temperature, the molar ratio of ammonium sulfate to tailings on the extraction of iron has been studied.

Key words: copper processing plant, waste, ammonium sulfate, iron compound.

Currently, the reserves of non-ferrous metals concentrated in the dumps and tailings dumps of Almalik MMC JSC amount to hundreds of millions of tons. In particular, about 150 million tons of substandard off-balance sheet ores have accumulated in the dumps.

Among non-ferrous metallurgy enterprises, the main burden on the atmosphere (in terms of emissions) is provided by JSC UMMC, whose emissions account for more than 60% of the release of polluted substances into the atmosphere of the entire industry of Almalik-Angren district. To determine the technological parameters of processing the tailings of the UMMC copper processing plant, the quantitative content of chemical elements in them was determined. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the waste from the copper processing plant.

Table 1

Chemical composition of waste from the AGMK copper processing plant

No	Elements	Percentage of elements, %	Elements	Percentage of elements, %
1	Al	5.08	Sr	0.0372
2	Fe	52.6	Pb	0.535

The tailings of the copper processing plant contain the largest amount of iron. The purpose of the study is to determine the degree of iron extraction from the tailings of the processing plant of JSC MMC. For the study, tailings from the OA AGMK copper processing plant were selected, which were sent for grinding into a ball mill. The result was shown with a sample dimension of -0.071 mm, which has a high degree of magnetic attraction. Based on this, an experiment using ammonium sulfate was conducted to extract iron from waste. The results of the experiment showed that Fe was obtained under the following conditions: the molar ratio of ammonium sulfate to iron-containing waste is 3:1, the firing

temperature is 800°C, the firing time in the furnace is 240 minutes and the size of the resulting waste is 200 microns.

A sample weighing 400 g and with a grain size of +0.200 mm, which consists of waste and crushed ammonium sulfate in a ratio of 3:1, was thoroughly mixed and loaded into a muffle furnace and fired at 800 ° C for 240 minutes (Fig. 2). Further, the sample was cooled after firing and sent to microscopic analysis (Fig. 3), then to the laboratory of the Institute of Mineral Resources at the Geological University to obtain the results of analysis using atomic emission spectroscopy, the data are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 2. Muffle furnace. The firing process at a temperature of 800°C

Table 3 shows that the degree of reduction of iron oxides with the use of ammonium sulfate was: Fe 3.4 g / t, This is well illustrated in Figure No. 3. Processing of tailings of a copper processing plant can be carried out with the use of ammonium sulfate, which thereby contribute to reducing the cost of their processing.

Fig.3. Microscopic analysis

Table 3.

Results of atomic emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma (NPP - ISP), g/t

Material	Content of elements, g/t							
Sample No. 1	Al	As	Ba	Be	Bi**	Ca	Cd	Ce

	53000	<1,0	128	1,68	1,96	3700	0,122	8,93
	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	K	Li	Lu	Mg
	3,24	84,7	567	33800	21300	11,5	0,186	7120

Literatures

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